

tone in generative phonology

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Predictable Variation & Redundancy

- Benjamin Elugbe

Part I Predictable Variation

I deliberately delayed the writing of this paper until the discussions of the first day of our meeting had been concluded. This appeared to me necessary in view of the nature of this aspect of our discussion.

First of all, I thought that by doing this, I should be avoiding a great deal of duplication of arguments. For example, predictable variation is of at least two types: allotonic or morphotonemic. I understand, however, that we shall here be concerned only with allotonic variation. This means, then, that this aspect had in fact come under discussion yesterday, witness our discussion of lowered tones and gliding tones.

Allotonic variation of tone may result in lowering or raising of tone, though it appears that such so-called raising, if not the result of intonation, can usually be explained in terms of lowering (Thomas 1967). For example, when we observe that in a sequence High-Low-High the second High is lower than the first, we are dealing (even if indirectly) with a case of allotonic variation. I suggest that such a phenomenon, since it usually results in down-drift, be handled as in the cases of downstep/down-drift. The question may arise of what to do with cases such as in Oke-Agbẹ where no environment (diachronic or synchronic) can be given to explain an apparent lowering of a tone. As at now, there is no way of explaining this - such languages await further investigation.

If as suggested by Dr. Kay Williamson, the feature [downdrift] is unnecessary, we may yet account for downdrift by inserting a rule which will add or subtract one from the numerical value of each High tone preceded by a Low tone. The issue is between having a downdrift feature, or the pitch adjustment rule mentioned above. Since it is not likely that we can ultimately do without such a rule, I would think that we do away with the downdrift feature. In this way we may have the following rules to account for the lowering of tones instead of the downdrift rules of Voorhoeve et al.

- 1 ~ $\begin{bmatrix} + \text{ Raised} \\ - \text{ Raised} \end{bmatrix}$ \rightarrow ~ $\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 3 \end{bmatrix}$ / # —
- 2 $\begin{bmatrix} n \\ \alpha \text{ Raised} \end{bmatrix}$ \rightarrow [n + 1] / $\begin{bmatrix} n \\ \alpha \text{ Raised} \end{bmatrix}$ —
- 3 $\begin{bmatrix} - \text{ Seg} \\ n \end{bmatrix}$ \rightarrow \emptyset

Rule one assigns numerical values to every High and Low. Rule two adds one to the value of a tone if it is not the first of its kind in the string. Thus we can derive from /kofi nhyé kawá/ 'kofi does not wear a ring' the following:

kofi nhyé kawá
 3 1 3 1 3 1 by rule 1
 3 1 4 2 5 3 by rule 2

This rule will not be reapplied to the leftmost segment of the preceding application.

The question of gliding tones also comes under predictable variation. We saw yesterday that a gliding tone can result from a contraction of two tones. Even the

question of tones not arising from apparent contraction has been discussed and it appears that the approach by which we postulate a nonsegmental Low tone (possibly High in rising tones) was favoured. I have no objections to this. But I should like to raise once more the issue of predictable gliding tones which are supposedly not grammatically motivated. In Ghotuḡ (an Edo language) all prepausal High or Mid tones are falling if they are realized on a verb. Thus:

[ɔ́ dá òkpòsò] 'he took a wife'
 [- - -]
 [òkpòsò ɔ́ dá] 'he took a wife' (emphatic)
 [- - -]

With this compare [ɔ́ gbé íní] 'he killed an elephant', where the final high on a noun is not falling.

If we allow two features [Rising] and [Falling], we can capture this fact simply (using [Raised] and [Lowered] in the sense in which Maddieson used them yesterday):

[
 × Raised
 - Lowered] → [+ Falling] / [..._V [-]_V]_{VP} #

With regard to the cases of gliding tones resulting from contractions, we would then adopt Mr. Shimizu's first approach which is that of admitting the features [Rising] and [Falling]. That, perhaps, is a question of morphotonemics which, happily, is outside the scope of my discussion.

This approach has its disadvantages and one may, therefore, consider the other proposal - that of having a rule which will insert a Low tone after every prepausal High or Mid on a verb, such a rule would have to be very late

and would be of the nature:

$$\emptyset \rightarrow \left[\begin{array}{l} - \text{ Raised} \\ + \text{ Lowered} \end{array} \right] / \left[\begin{array}{l} \alpha \text{ Raised} \\ - \text{ Lowered} \end{array} \right] \text{---}]_V \quad \neq$$

Each of the proposals has got its merits and demerits and I cannot say which is preferable. However, our framework must take other tone languages with inherent gliding tones into consideration. Whether we can postulate fictitious, irrecoverable high and low pitches at every turn is doubtful. Worse still, it is far from clear whether it accounts for the facts to say that all gliding tones (inherent or otherwise) are sequences of level pitches.

On the other hand, by adopting the second proposal, we avoid a certain amount of redundancy. For example, in Wukari Jukun only four types of glides occur where we have the possibility of six. Moreover, when we use the features [Rising] or [Falling] with other specifications (e.g.

mid-falling is $\left[\begin{array}{l} - \text{ Raised} \\ - \text{ Lowered} \\ + \text{ Falling} \end{array} \right]$) we may end up with specifications

such as $\left[\begin{array}{l} + \text{ Raised} \\ + \text{ Lowered} \\ + \text{ Falling} \end{array} \right]$ (high falling to Low). The point is

that even in a glide we tend (tacitly) to hold the idea of linearity: high followed by low, indicated by the feature [Falling].

There is a type of predictable variation which I have not mentioned here at all. Sometimes, a High tone may be low or lowered depending on whether or not it is followed or preceded by a voiceless/voiced consonant or sonorant/obstruent etc. I have no examples and I have not looked

into this.

Part II Redundancy

I mentioned earlier that for one or two reasons I had to base the introduction of this discussion on yesterday's discussions. This was particularly necessary in discussing redundancy. For, by using Mr. Maddieson's features in the ensuing discussion we shall certainly be achieving a measure of continuity. Let me say, however, that I did not feel bound to employ Mr. Maddieson's suggested features. But the neatness and economy which they introduce into the framework - as opposed to Wang's - has appealed a great deal to me. It is his treatment of gliding tones, adopted from Miss Woo, that I feel is open to question.

In discussing tonal redundancy - the fact that certain tonological feature specifications are predictable, given others - we have to distinguish between universal redundancy and language-specific redundancy. This means that we have to distinguish between a set of universal conventions to deal with universal redundancy, and language-specific tonal redundancy rules.

First, the conventions. Below is reproduced the matrix as given yesterday by Mr. Maddieson:

	Mid	High	Low	EH	EL	*1	*2	*3
Raised	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	-
Lowered	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-
Extreme	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	+

With three features we have a total of eight possible specifications. So far, however, only five distinctive

pitch levels have been discovered for any tone language anywhere. The remaining three non-occurring specifications are a logical consequence of the features we have chosen. For this redundancy, we need the following conventions:

- 1 $\begin{bmatrix} + & L \\ \times & E \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow [-R]$
- 2 $\begin{bmatrix} - & R \\ - & L \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow [-E]$
- 3 $\begin{bmatrix} + & R \\ \times & E \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow [-L]$
- 4 $[+E] \rightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [+R] \\ [+L] \end{array} \right\}$

While these conventions deal with the universal redundancy of the system, lexical redundancy rules will differ from language to language. For example in Ghotuq no lexical items with a VCV structure have the tonal pattern Low-High and none begin with a High tone. Hence all initials in VCV items are [-Raised], and if the second syllabic is [+Raised] then the initial must be [-Lowered] i.e. Mid tone. Language-specific redundancy rules are required to account for these and similar facts.

If all languages operated identical tonal systems, every type of redundancy would be universal. But greater redundancy arises the greater the complexity of the systems we wish to describe within our framework. If for example all languages operated a two-tone system, redundancy would be minimal and we would have, perhaps, only one tone feature [Lowered] or [Raised].

A language which operates an optimal three tone system is redundantly marked for the feature [Extreme]. Such redundancy is taken care of by the following conventions:-

$$1 \begin{bmatrix} \alpha H \\ \beta L \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow [-E]$$

$$2 [+H] \rightarrow [-L]$$

This type of redundancy will be universal to all languages operating such a three-tone system, apart from their individual lexical redundancy rules.

Three types of redundancy are thus identified. The first is universal and, therefore, requires conventions. The second is language-specific and requires language-specific redundancy rules. The last is redundancy characteristic of different tonological systems and requires partially universal conventions. The first type derives from the actual "phonetic meaning" or our features; the second from language-specific limitations imposed on tonal combinations within items; and the third from the actual diversity of tonological systems.

DISCUSSION

- I.M. I should just like to raise a point connected with your willingness of accept ordering features like [Rising] and [Falling]. If this is done then the logical thing is to accept that diphthongs should also be indicated as a single segment and marked [+ Diphthong] or [+ Closing] or [+ Centring] or whatever. The interconnection of the two things has been seen by Afolayan (1970) when he brings gliding pitches and diphthongs together under the general label of glides in Yoruba.
- K.S. One often finds that a contraction of two syllables produces a diphthong with a gliding pitch. Clearly one kind of contraction rule is needed to cover both.
- O.O. The formulation of the downdrift rule in association with the Twi example is wrong. If n is 1 and the following Low

tone is $n + 1$ then that makes its value 2 not 4. It requires some formulation like this:-

$$\begin{bmatrix} n \\ \propto R \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow n + 1 \quad / \quad \begin{bmatrix} n \\ \propto R \end{bmatrix} \quad \left(\begin{bmatrix} m \\ -\propto R \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad -$$

Where n and m are different numbers.

B.E. The use of n was intended to refer to any value of a number and the important thing is that after a tone of a different type the numerical value of the syllable changes.